

Advancing Strategic Resilience through Cybersecurity in Sustainability Practices

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the framework of the project No. No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007 "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" of the second round of the Consolidation and Governance Change Implementation Grants within Investment 5.2.1.1.i "Research, Development and Consolidation Grants" under Reform 5.2.1.r "Higher Education and Science Excellence and Governance Reform" of Reform and Investment Strand 5.2 of the Latvian Recovery and Resilience Mechanism Plan "Ensuring Change in the Governance Model of Higher Education Institutions", research grant project No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0032 "Advancing Strategic Resilience through Cybersecurity in Sustainability Practices" (project manager: Dr, prof. Līga Peiseniece, 1st September 2024 – 28st February 2026).

Project summary:

The project aims to investigate the interrelationship between sustainable cybersecurity, sustainability reporting, the strategic resilience of companies and assess preparedness for integration the cybersecurity and sustainability, and the sustainability reporting to facilitate the strategic resilience of companies. The research object is medium and large companies listed at Nasdaq Baltic from the 1st and 2nd lists or issuing bonds complying and falling within the requirement to ensure sustainability reports. This project's scientific credibility, excellence and novelty are characterised by an interdisciplinarity approach in analysing sustainable cybersecurity (CS) as an enabler of strategic resilience, combining risk management, CS management, sustainability, governance and other management studies disciplines. The project will be implemented by a team of researchers and PhD students from two higher education and research institutions: BA School of Business and Finance (BASBF) as an applicant and University of Latvia (LU) as the cooperation partner. The research project will generate several scientific results: one scientific publication, two international conference abstracts, one functional framework for businesses for accessing

the sustainable CS elements and its integration with sustainable development (SD) of medium and large companies, one project proposal for submission in an international or national call for research projects, research results contribute to the preparation of two PhD thesis and quantitative data set of the survey results of medium and large companies on existing practices, shortages and necessary improvements regarding CS, SD and sustainability reporting. The project seeks lasting changes and effects in academic communities, business and practitioner networks, governmental organisations, civil society and the wider public.

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Internal and External
Consolidation of the University
of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia, BA School of Business and Finance

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Advancing Strategic Resilience through Cybersecurity in Sustainability Practices](#)

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia
(5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: CyberSustain

3. License

License: AFL-3.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

WP1: Project management, monitoring & impact assessment

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

2 Research Data Management

3 Resources and Security

WP2: Exploration and conceptualisation

T2.1: To perform a critical literature analysis on sustainable CS, SD, sustainability reporting and ESG, business sustainability and strategic resilience

T2.2: Based on the literature analysis, to develop a theoretical model of research

D2.1: Literature analysis and the theoretical research model

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

WP3 Empirical study and synthesis of results

T3.1: To develop questionnaire and pilot survey

T3.2: To survey managers of medium and large companies listed at Nasdaq Baltic

D3.1: Results of the empirical research

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

WP4: Elaboration and approbation of the functional framework

T4.1: To prepare guidelines for expert interviews and conduct expert interviews to explain empirical research results

T4.2: To develop a functional framework on accessing the sustainable CS elements and its integration with SD

T4.3: Stakeholder co-creation workshop on the applicability of the functional framework

T4.4: Elaboration of recommendation for relevant stakeholders

D4.1: The functional framework and recommendations for industry and other relevant stakeholders

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

WP5: Dissemination and knowledge sharing

T5.1: To prepare and submit the scientific article

T5.2: To report in scientific conferences and other professional events

T5.3. To update the study programmes and courses

T5.4: Dissemination activities

D5.1: The scientific article prepared in scientific journal indexed in SCOPUS/ Web of Science

D5.2. At least 2 reports in scientific conferencesWP6

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 [Data Summary](#)

2 [Research Data Management](#)

3 [Resources and Security](#)

WP6: Horizons of the future research proposal

T6.1: Networking and involvement of partners

T6.2: Project idea design according to the project call

T6.3: Preparation and submission of the project proposal

D6.1: The new research project proposal submitted

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[2 Research Data Management](#)

[3 Resources and Security](#)

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